

User Survey Questions

Section 1: Demographic Questions

- In what age group are you?
- To which gender identity do you most identify as?
- In which country do you currently reside?
- What is your highest educational qualification?

Section 2: Health Status

- Has a health care provider ever told you have a chronic disease?
- What chronic disease do you have?

Section 3: mHealth Applications

- Have you used mHealth applications before to manage your chronic disease?
- What kind of mHealth application(s) have you used before?
- Why do you mainly use these application(s) for?
- How frequently do you use health applications?
- How long each time you use the app?

Section 4: Adaptive User Interface

- Which kind of adaptation do you prefer for interface adaptation?
- Which types of data should be used for adapting mHealth applications? (Select all that apply)
- How do you wish your data to be collected? (Select all that apply)
- What level of initiative do you prefer in the adaptation process?

Additional Questions

- How did you hear about us?
- Is there anything else you want to tell us about this survey or our research study?
- Would you like us to email you the survey result?